

**IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR
PERAPICAL TISSUE INFLAMMATION IN PREGNANT
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ABSTRACT

This article is about the development of complex measures aimed at treating pregnant women with odontogenic inflammatory diseases. Odontogenic inflammations can harm not only the mother's body, but also the developing fetus. The development of diagnostic algorithms and new approaches to the treatment of inflammatory processes in the maxillofacial region in pregnant women remains very relevant, which became the basis for conducting this study. As a result of odontogenic inflammation, changes occur in the composition of the general blood, urine, amniotic fluid in the pregnant body. Identifying the pathogenic microflora and correctly selecting the necessary group of antibiotics increases the effectiveness of treatment.

This article is about the development of complex measures aimed at treating pregnant women with odontogenic inflammatory diseases. Odontogenic inflammations can harm not only the mother's body, but also the developing fetus. The development of diagnostic algorithms and new approaches to the treatment of inflammatory processes in the maxillofacial region in pregnant women remains very relevant, which became the basis for conducting this study. As a result of odontogenic inflammation, changes occur in the composition of the general blood, urine, amniotic fluid in the pregnant body. Identifying the pathogenic microflora and correctly selecting the necessary group of antibiotics increases the effectiveness of treatment.

Introduction.**Prevalence and risk factors of dental diseases in pregnant women.**

The organization and implementation of dental care for the population plays a major role in the formation of dental health of pregnant women. During pregnancy, women experience a load on all organs and systems of the body, including teeth. An established system of dental care in the form of planned oral hygiene during pregnancy has a positive effect on the early detection of oral diseases and provides an opportunity to begin their treatment and prevention. The implementation of therapeutic and preventive procedures for pregnant women allows you to maintain the health of the mother and create adequate conditions for the intrauterine development of the child. The literature on the study of this issue notes that oral pathologies in pregnant women lead to mortality and the presence of chronic foci of infection in the general somatic and oral cavity [6; pp. 65-68].

Indian scientists (Palupi, R., Juzika, O., Romadhoni, S.F. 2019) argue that severe periodontal disease in a pregnant woman can produce inflammatory mediators that threaten the fetal placenta, thereby increasing the likelihood of premature birth. The authors present the results of an analytical study of pregnant women of the Javanese ethnic group in Surabaya, Indonesia. The sample was calculated using a simple random sampling method and consisted of 49 pregnant women. The data obtained were analyzed using the Spearman correlation test and the multiple linear regression test.

The author (Korneeva M.V. et al., 2015) noted that among the complex issues of practical dentistry is the treatment of patients with chronic destructive forms of periodontitis. In recent years, it has been proven that the somatic background affects the frequency and severity of the clinical course of inflammatory processes in the oral cavity and periapical tissues. 47 women (18-30 years old) with indications for surgical treatment of chronic apical periodontitis were examined. At the same time, the exclusion criteria were cholesterol, systemic connective tissue diseases, women taking hormonal contraceptives, pregnant women, abortions, childbirth, women who were lactating less than a year ago. The authors assessed the degree of damage to periapical tissues and the postoperative period depending on the violation of iron metabolism. Red blood cell and iron metabolism indicators were studied, and iron metabolism disorders were identified in the pathogenesis of purulent-inflammatory periodontal diseases. Against the background of iron metabolism disorders in periapical tissues, inflammatory and destructive processes develop rapidly, and the regularity of the complicated course of the postoperative period is determined. Established criteria for a poor prognosis in the postoperative period in patients with chronic periodontitis. Iron deficiency contributes to more extensive damage to periapical tissues and the development of complications in the postoperative period [6; pp. 65-68].

According to the literature, the most dangerous critical periods of embryogenesis in dental caries are 1-3 and 3-16 weeks of embryogenesis. Taking medications during such periods can lead to the death of the embryo or the formation of anomalies. In the 1st trimester of pregnancy, preventive sanitation of the oral cavity is planned: the selection of means and methods for personal oral hygiene, professional hygiene to prevent inflammatory diseases of the periodontal complex tissues, sparing methods of treating diseases of hard dental tissues. These measures should be carried out in the 2nd-3rd trimester with a frequency of 1-2 times per trimester.

Materials and methods

The study involved 25 pregnant women aged 19 to 41 years (mean age 24.5 ± 3.4 years). The inclusion criteria were: hospitalization for various odontogenic inflammatory processes in the maxillofacial area for the treatment of odontogenic inflammatory diseases and their complications. The exclusion criteria were non-pregnant women, children under 18 years of age and men. In the Department of Adult Maxillofacial Surgery of the Tashkent State Dental Institute, pregnant women were provided with urgent surgical and complex treatment procedures. Surgical and postoperative care for pregnant women was carried out in trimesters, taking into account the characteristics of each period of the expectant mother's body and the fetus.

Depending on the treatment and preventive measures taken, all patients were divided into 2 groups:

Group 1 (main) - 13 pregnant women, in addition to the background of traditional medicine treatment, after opening the purulent focus, determining the sensitivity of the sample to antibiotics, Chlorophyllipt solution and the drug "Cefoperazone+Sulbactam 2.0" 2.0 g every 12 hours, m/o.

Group 2 (control) - 12 pregnant women, after opening the purulent focus, Chlorophyllipt solution and the drug "Ceftriaxone" 1.0 g every 8 hours m/o

The study used microscopic examination to calculate the results of a general blood test taken from patients. The method of counting the number of white blood cells in a smear stained according to Romanovsky-Giemsa was used.

During the surgical procedure, a sample of purulent material from the local area was sent to the microbiology laboratory to determine the bacterial strain, colony, and antibiotic sensitivity. In order to study the effect of odontogenic inflammatory processes on the fetus, pregnant women were initially subjected to a transabdominal ultrasound screening examination before surgery. The examination determined the sex of the fetus, duration, organ development, placental status, and amniotic fluid parameters. The examinations were conducted before surgery and 7 days after the procedure.

Results of the study

One of the main changes in the general blood test of patients before and after the treatment was the leukocyte index, which was observed to increase in inflammatory processes in the main and control groups. In the main group, the number of leukocytes changed from the initial (15.36 ± 1.42 g/l), to the 3rd day after the operation and procedures (11.16 ± 1.02 g/l) and the 7th day (7.16 ± 0.92 g/l). In the control group, the number of leukocytes decreased from the initial (15.96 ± 1.44 g/l) to the 3rd day after the operation and procedures (12.86 ± 1.24 g/l) and the 7th day (10.06 ± 1.04 g/l).

Another indicator of inflammatory processes, the erythrocyte sedimentation rate, was normal in the main group of patients at baseline (17.85 ± 1.52 mm/s), on the 3rd day after surgery (15.36 ± 1.22 mm/s), and on the 7th day (8.36 ± 0.92). In the control group, the pre-treatment indicator (17.97 ± 1.24 mm/s) decreased to (15.87 ± 1.18 mm/s) and (10.84 ± 1.28 mm/s) on the 3rd and 7th days after surgery and medication.

In a sample of purulent discharge obtained during surgery, various gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial colonies were detected during bacteriological examination. In the samples taken from the main and control groups, (54%) *Staphylococcus aureus* colonies, (13%) *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, (11%) *Streptococcus pyogenes*, (8%) *Escherichia coli* and other types of bacterial colonies were found. The sensitivity of these bacterial colonies to antibacterial drugs belonging to different groups was determined. The highest index was determined in the drug "Cefaperazon + sulbactam 2.0". (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*) colonies were (2.78 ± 0.17 and 2.65 ± 0.21 , respectively). In the drug "Ceftraxion 1.0" used in the control group, the indices were (2.04 ± 0.18 and 1.98 ± 0.12 , respectively).

In all examined pregnant patients, no fetal pathology was detected during the initial ultrasound screening examination. After operative and complex treatment procedures, no

pathological changes were detected in the parameters of the main group of patients. In the control group, a slight turbidity of the amniotic fluid remained.

Conclusions

1. Based on a retrospective analysis, the number of hospitalizations of pregnant women with purulent inflammatory conditions in the maxillofacial region in odontogenic acute inflammatory processes was determined;

2. The high diagnostic value of determining the antibiotic sensitivity of a purulent sample in odontogenic inflammatory diseases, the results of general blood, urine, biochemical analysis and fetal UTT screening examination has been proven;

3. The effectiveness of treatment measures increases compared to traditional treatment when the drug "Cefaperazon + sulbactam 2.0" is included in complex treatment in pregnant women.

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